

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE STATUS OF A TEACHER: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

Ergashev Azizjon Yigitaliyevych

Independent researcher of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10653778>

Abstract: In the article, the socio-philosophical aspects of securing the status of a pedagogue, its necessity, current issue, and its socio-philosophical classification and specific features were analyzed in this process.

Key words: pedagogue, status of pedagogue, integration, globalization, social, philosophical, transformation.

INTRODUCTION

Today, many legal documents have been adopted by the leadership of our country in order to educate a competent generation in the country, which, first of all, in these documents, educate the youth of the future as a generation that is competent in all aspects, physically healthy, mentally mature and will make a great contribution to the development of the country. is set as a goal. In order to increase the status of the pedagogue in society, to regulate the legal, social and economic relations related to the activity, to create conditions for his professional development and to ensure his legal guarantees, several legal bases were developed. The importance of studying the social position of the teacher is that his role in society is extremely high in almost any historical situation. The special importance of the teacher's social position is determined by his functions in the process of social reproduction and socialization of new generations.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Researchers such as V.P. Bezdukhov, E.P. Belozertsev, E.V. Bondarevskaya, N.M. Boritko, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, E.F. Zer, L.B. Itelson, Yu.N.A. Kulyutkin, V.S.S. Sukhobskaya have conducted scientific research on the description of the teacher's status and its formation. Consideration of the place and role of the teacher in the social structure of modern society is related to the determination of the institutional functions of the educational system as a social institution. Social institutions and their tasks are analyzed in the works of M. Weber, T. Veblen, E. Durkheim, R. Darendorf, T. Parsons, G. Spencer, J. Smelser, J. Shepanski and others.

In addition, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Status of the Pedagogue" serves as the main source.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 21st century is the age of specialists with high intellectual potential, modern knowledge and skills, a new outlook and independent thinking. The service of teachers in raising such a generation is incomparable. Because now in the world, the level of development of the country is determined by the position of pedagogues in the society. Science and education is a problem that will solve the society and the state today, but also tomorrow. Therefore, in our country, great attention is being paid to this issue at the state level. Where youth education is left to its own devices, society will decline.

The status of a pedagogue is recognized in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Organizational and legal conditions are created for pedagogues to carry out their professional activities, their social protection is ensured and guarantees are given for the realization of their rights.

The rights, honor, dignity and professional reputation of the teacher are under the protection of the state [1].

The pedagogue is invited to activities unrelated to his professional activity, but of political and social importance (participation in the process of organizing and holding elections, acting as an audience monitor during tests, assisting in population registration, to participate as an expert in the process of inspection and certification of educational organizations, etc.) according to his consent, based on the contract concluded with him, for an additional fee, during his free time or at his place of work. The average salary is kept.

Administratively forcing a pedagogue to work in any form, as well as unlawfully interfering with a pedagogue's professional activity or preventing him from fulfilling his service obligations, is a cause of liability in accordance with the law [1].

Modern society is solving important problems related to achieving the goals of sustainable development and creating opportunities for the rapid formation of the young generation. This society is characterized as an information technology and communication civilization, in which knowledge and information are given priority. As a result, the educational system turns out to be one of the main systems for society, and its representatives should play an important role in the social practical system.

The teacher, as the main person of the institution of social education, is at the center of social changes affecting the quality of the "answers" given by the society to the historical "calls". Education and its employees are necessary to ensure the functioning of all subsystems of social development. In this regard, it is difficult to understand the dysfunctional state of educational structures (low production quality, insufficient assessment of social importance, national and regional savings on education and other wrong social strategies regarding education).

The education system is the main social institution that determines the level of development of society. In order for this institution to successfully fulfill its tasks, it should not only meet the requirements of the time, but also have the ability to advance development.

Fundamental changes in the economic and political system of Uzbekistan led to significant changes in public consciousness, individual and public psychology, and values.

The transformation processes taking place in modern society make the question of how different socio-professional groups adapt to the new situation more urgent. Among them, the pedagogical corps of the society occupies an important place.

The teacher is the main link and subject that determines success and failure in education. He is confident in the future, satisfied with his work, effectively fulfills his professional duties and serves as an important factor in the stability and consistent development of the educational system and the entire society. The state of the teacher's social well-being is a known indicator of the effectiveness of reforming society as a system. Therefore, at present, it is very important to systematically understand the living conditions and activities of the teacher, to objectively evaluate his place and role in society. For this purpose, a sociological analysis of the socio-economic status of teachers as a specific socio-professional group, their place and role in the social structure of society, conditions of

professional activity, adaptation to the status in the region, their social well-being and changes in their value directions is very important. is important.

Adaptation to the status is a category, the study of which allows to record the staticity of the position and role of teachers, as well as the dynamics of their social position, the change of value orientations. These processes are not always directed in a positive direction in the conditions of social instability, development of conflicts in various spheres, increase of social risk and social tension, sharp social stratification, crisis of social regulation mechanisms. All this makes the adaptation process of intellectuals, especially teachers, whose social and economic situation is deteriorating according to the main indicators, whose social status is supported by "internal energy" urgent. Education is one of the main factors contributing to the sustainable and safe development of society. With all the different meaningful interpretations of the concept of "education", it should be noted that, first of all, education is a social institution that performs a number of important social functions. Teachers are real participants in the educational process and play a leading role in education. The importance of their role and functions determines the position of a certain socio-professional group in society.

A person's social mood, his social relations with other people, his interests and relations, his attitude to his role in society is related to his place in the social stratification system. Assessment of social status is determined by a person's personal contribution to social production. The demand for labor results and their appropriate assessment by society actively encourages the creative potential of a person and its professional realization.

Researchers hardly distinguish status adjustment from social adjustment types. As a basis for determining status adaptation, we can suggest a state of satisfaction with socio-demographic characteristics of a person, his position in the system of socio-economic relations and everyday life. The category of adaptation to the situation allows us to solve the problem of behavioral algorithms and strategies used by certain social groups and communities to maintain their position.

The decline in the prestige of the teaching profession in society and the state has led to the departure of young people from the field of education and the departure of men to other areas of professional activity.

Unsatisfactory working conditions and low wages are factors that negatively affect the process of adapting the position of teachers to the modern socio-economic situation. Many of them, especially young people, develop a weak attachment to school, which affects their attitude to work, pessimistic mood, and desire to change their profession.

A modern teacher strives to express himself in the professional sphere, but this contradicts his real position. And, of course, the material factor has a significant impact on teachers' attitude to their profession.

CONCLUSION

Despite all the diversity of views on education, experience shows that the foundations of culture are laid in the early years. That is why all nations highly value the place of the teacher in the life of the society. Educators are subjects of growing personality formation and reflect the specific characteristics of ideas about educational goals in each historical period. People change society, and education changes people. At the center of education is the teacher. If we want to raise the educational work to a higher level, we must first of all raise the social status of teachers, teachers, mentors. Because, first of all, high development and well-being can be

achieved thanks to great attention to science and education. The most important goal and task facing our country is to join the ranks of developed democracies in the world, to build a free and prosperous way of life for our people.

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the status of a teacher" - 2024. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6786401>
2. Ануфриев Е. А. Социальный статус и активность личности. М.: Мысль, 1984. - 123 с.
3. Вершловский С. Г. Учитель о себе и о профессии. JL: Знание, 1988.-32 с.
3. Герасимова Н. В. Социальная адаптация пожилых людей к современной ситуации: Автореф дис. . канд. социол. наук. Саранск, 2001. -25 с.
4. Гибадуллина, Ю.М. Профессиональная подготовка педагогов в процессе интеграции формального, неформального и информального образования / Ю.М.Гибадуллина // Фундаментальные исследования. – 2014. – № 11 (10). – С. 2253-2256 (0,4 п.л.).
5. Стародубцева Л. Динамика социального статуса педагогов: На примере Республики Мордовия. Автореферат дисс. канд. социол. наук. Саранск, 2003.

